

TEACHER'S PERCEPTION OF INNOVATION PROCESSES IN EDUCATION

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10389682>

Annotation. The article reveals the problem of teachers' readiness for innovations in education. The receptivity to the new, to self-education, as well as the level of innovation of teachers are presented.

Keywords: innovation; innovative activity; teachers' readiness to innovate.

Recently, education has been in the midst of modernization and innovation. Currently, the innovation process is acquiring a special status. In this regard, the mastery by teachers of new target orientations of the educational process, the development and transformation of the professional competence of teaching staff become a necessary condition for the activities of educational organizations.

The problem of teachers' attitude to innovative processes in the field of education includes the attitude to work in modern conditions related to the content of the activity itself, self-esteem, self-organization, as well as the perception of innovation as necessary changes in the nature of the public demand for changing the role of the individual in social progress.

In this regard, we made an attempt to analyze the attitude of teachers to innovative processes in teaching. The study was conducted by studying scientific articles that are publicly available on the Internet.

Teachers' perceptions of innovation, in our study, include receptivity and openness to new things, self-education, and the level of innovation of teachers.

An analysis of numerous articles on the Internet showed that teachers often note in their answers that they are constantly engaged in self-education, often adhere to certain pedagogical ideas, and develop them in the process of teaching. The lowest level of self-education is observed among students; this, in turn, was studied by V.A. Korvyakov. He found that "the vast majority of students showed a low level of development of skills in self-educational activity (64.6% and 62.5%), an average level - 33.3% and 35.4% (the greatest difficulties are associated with the skills of self-organization, obtaining and processing information)" [1].

Thus, the results of the study showed that students of civilian universities are less receptive to innovations in teaching activities, perhaps this is due to low motivation to work in their specialty and little work experience.

Trainee teachers doubt more than they believe in the new and prefer the old.

Based on the results, we developed the following recommendations:

1. Create the necessary motivational conditions for teachers' self-improvement (redirect the vector from material incentives to self-development).
2. Carrying out activities to inform teachers about innovations in the field of education.

3. Mutual attendance at lessons in order to analyze the effectiveness of the innovative pedagogical technologies used.
4. Organization of events aimed at resolving conflict situations in the teaching staff and interaction of all participants in the teaching process.

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